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## Quantifying Chronological Inconsistencies of Archaeological Sites in the Petra Area
## - The Nabataean Period (Example) -
## =====
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## Version: 01
## Date of last changes: Sat 26 Nov 18:41:44 CET 2016
## Data: XLSX-Table of archaeological sites in the Petra area from the Iron Age to
## Byzantine Periods (including fuzzy and Boolean dating values per cultural period
## and their corresponding time spans)
## Author of data: Various surveys in the Petra Hinterland including Abudanh 2006, ARNAS,
## FJHP (Extended and Core Area), JSS, ShamAyl, Smith 2010, WMWS 1996 and 1998 as well as
## PHSP 2016 (compare table 1 in text for bibliographical reference)
## Purpose: Quantification of differing chronological definitions of cultural periods
## by the various surveys

#####
## Packages
##=====
##install.packages("xlsx")
##install.packages("sqldf")
##install.packages("tcltk")
##install.packages("ggplot2")
library(xlsx)
library(sqldf)
library(tcltk)
library(ggplot2)

#####
## References
##=====
##citation(package="xlsx"):
##Adrian A. Dragulescu (2014). xlsx: Read, write, format Excel 2007 and Excel
##97/2000/XP/2003 files. R package version 0.5.7.
##http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=xlsx

## citation(package="sqldf"):
##G. Grothendieck (2014). sqldf: Perform SQL Selects on R Data Frames. R package
##version 0.4-10. http://CRAN.R-project.org/package=sqldf

##citation(package="tcltk"):
##R Core Team (2015). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R
##Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL
##https://www.R-project.org/.

##citation(package="ggplot2"):
##H. Wickham. ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis. Springer-Verlag New York,
##2009.

#####
## Working Directory
##=====
setwd("Y:/directory")

#####
## Read Base Data (XLSX-table as stated above)
##=====
library(xlsx)
df<- read.xlsx("table of all archaeological sites.xlsx", 1)

#####
## Extracting Single Cultural Periods and Respective Max. Time Spans (Century-based)
##=====
##Example: The Nabataean Period:

S_N<- data.frame(sqldf('select * from df where "100 BC" > 0 or "100 AD" > 0 or
"200 AD" > 0 or
"300 AD" > 0 or "400 AD" > 0')) ## NOTE:"100 BC" etc.
## refer to 1. century BC etc.

## write xlsx table for Nabataean Period only:
write.xlsx(S_N, "./directory/table of Nabataean period.xlsx", sheetName = "Sheet1")

#####
## Summing All Fuzzy and Boolean Dating Values Per Cultural Period
## And Their Max. Time Spans
##=====
N_dating<- cbind(length(df$N[df$N>0]),
sum(N[,42]), sum(N[,43]), sum(N[,44]), sum(N[,45]),
sum(N[,46]), sum(N[,47]))
colnames(N_dating)<- c("N Sites", "200 BC", "100 BC", "100 AD", "200 AD",
"300 AD", "400 AD")

## write table with Summed Dating Values for the Nabataean Period:

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write.xlsx(N_dating, "./directory/SumDv_N.xlsx", sheetName = "Sheet1")

#####
## Express as percentage by multiplying SumDv values with "pdec":

p<- 0.1366120218579235 ## = 1 percent value of all Nabataean sites
pdec<- p/100 ##divded by 100 for expression in decimal numbers

## save as new table "N_prob.xlsx"

#####
## Plotting Dating Graphs
#####
N<-read.xlsx("N_prob.xlsx", 1)

Nplot<- ggplot(N, aes(x=Decade, y= Probability, group= 1))+
  geom_line(colour= "black", size=1)+
  geom_ribbon(aes(ymin=0, ymax=Probability), alpha=0.4)+
  scale_x_discrete(limits= c("200 BC","190 BC","180 BC","170 BC","160 BC","150 BC",
    "140 BC","130 BC","120 BC","110 BC","100 BC","90 BC",
    "80 BC","70 BC","60 BC","50 BC","40 BC","30 BC","20 BC",
    "10 BC","0","10 AD","20 AD","30 AD","40 AD","50 AD", "60 AD",
    "70 AD", "80 AD","90 AD","100 AD","110 AD","120 AD",
    "130 AD", "140 AD","150 AD","160 AD","170 AD","180 AD",
    "190 AD","200 AD","210 AD","220 AD","230 AD", "240 AD",
    "250 AD","260 AD", "270 AD","280 AD","290 AD","300 AD",
    "310 AD", "320 AD"))+

  geom_vline(xintercept = which(N$Decade == "100 BC"), linetype = "longdash", size = 1)+

  geom_vline(xintercept = which(N$Decade == "110 AD"), linetype = "longdash", size = 1)+

  scale_y_discrete(limits= c(0, 0.25,0.5,0.75,1))+ ylim(0,1)+
  labs(x= "Decades", y="Probability", title= "Nabataean", size= 14 )+
  theme(text= element_text(size=25))+
  theme(axis.text.x = element_text(size = 20, angle = -90, hjust = 1))

ggsave(filename="./directory/Dating Graph_Nabataean Period.tiff", width=30, height=10,
  dpi = 800)

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